

Updated Academic Performance Audit (APA) Standards: Implications for Malaysian Polytechnic and Community Colleges

Norsalwati Mohd Razalli^{1*}, Zainal Ariffin Ahmad², Siti Zaine Zainal Abidin³, Hishamudin Musa⁴

^{1,3,4}Manjung Community College, 31, Persiaran PM 2/1, Pusat Bandar Seri Manjung Seksyen 2, 32000 Seri Manjung, Perak, Malaysia.

²Academy of Sciences Malaysia, 50480 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

*Corresponding author's email: sal010287@gmail.com

Abstract

In 2008, the Malaysian Qualifications Agency (MQA) developed the Code of Practice for Programme Accreditation (COPPA) as a standard guideline for Higher Education Providers (HEPs) in Malaysia. The COPPA ensures HEPs fulfill their mission and goals, identify areas of strengths and concerns, and improve quality. The Academic Performance Audit (APA) is essential to the COPPA quality assurance process. Over the years, HEPs have been experiencing developments that require institutional reforms to generate capable and innovative talents for the future economy as outlined in the 11th Malaysia Plan, Malaysia Education Blueprint 2015–2025 (Higher Education), and Malaysian Higher Education 4.0 (MyHE 4.0). Hence, MQA recently revised the COPPA cognizance of these reforms based on feedback from HEPs, assessors, quality assurance specialists, and regulators. Therefore, this study aims to explore the updated requirements of the APA and its implications for polytechnics and community colleges (PolyCCs) vying for MQA accreditation under the Department of Polytechnic and Community College Education (DPCCE). Currently, DPCCE adopts an internal audit guideline and auditors for Academic Assessment (PeNA) and Collegial and Ownership Monitoring (PK&K) for academic programmes offered at the certificate level. We employed an action research methodology in conducting this study. Based on document analysis, the revised COPPA 2017 has 98 standards and criteria stated under seven areas compared to 181 standards and criteria in nine areas of COPPA 2008. Data from APA audits conducted randomly at four HEPs on their certificate programmes were generalized to test whether the revised standards apply to PolyCCs. In conclusion, the study highlights four implications of the revised COPPA 2017 on the DPCCE, HEPs or PolyCCs, internal auditors, and the APA process in enhancing quality assurance among the polytechnic and community colleges in the Malaysian TVET (Technical and Vocational Education and Training) education ecosystem.

Keywords: Academic Performance Audit (APA), Code of Practice for Programme Accreditation (COPPA), Higher Education Providers (HEPs), polytechnic and community colleges (PolyCC), Malaysian TVET (Technical and Vocational Education and Training).

1. Introduction

Periodic institutional audits are an integral part of the quality assurance process within the Malaysian Higher Education system. These audits are mandated by the Malaysian Qualifications Agency (MQA) and play a significant role in ensuring institutions' ongoing quality and compliance. The Code of Practice for Institutional Audit (COPIA) identifies various institutional audits, including comprehensive, thematic, faculty-specific, and cross-faculty audits. The periodic Academic Performance Audit (APA), which assesses whether a program's accreditation status will be maintained or continued, is another type of institutional audit. Before undergoing an external assessment through an institutional audit, higher education providers (HEPs) conduct an internal quality audit to self-evaluate. This internal audit assesses the HEP's progress in achieving its mission and goals, identifying strengths and areas of concern, and ultimately working towards improving overall quality. As required by the MQA, the outcome of this internal quality audit is documented in a Self-Review Report for Institutional Audit. Before moving on, all relevant terms will be listed in the glossary at the end of this paper.

In 2011, Universiti Tenaga Nasional (UNITEN) conducted a study on its institutional audit in preparation for SETARA 2012, also known as the Rating System for Higher Education Institutions in Malaysia (Ahmad & Mohd Razalli, 2014). In the Code of Practice for Programme Accreditation (COPPA), nine areas were identified for benchmarking and enhancing standards. These areas include (1) vision, mission, educational goals, and learning outcomes, (2) curriculum design and delivery, (3) assessment of students, (4) student selection and support services, (5) academic staff, (6) educational resources, (7) programme monitoring and review, (8) leadership, governance, and administration, and (9) continual quality improvement. One hundred eighty-one standards were identified within these areas to ensure a comprehensive evaluation and enhancement of educational programs (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2008). However, these nine areas were reduced to seven in the revised COPPA 2017 in response to feedback from HEPs, assessors, quality assurance specialists, and regulators. MQA has implemented improvements, rationalizations, clarifications, and new measures to strengthen the COPPA with only 98 standards in seven areas (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2017). MQA also added information on the new standards with instructions for HEPs applying for provisional and full certification and added a novel self-review strategy for full accreditation employing an Excel tool. These improvements facilitated more efficient programme development, accreditation, management, and enhancement advice (Nordin et al., 2013) for HEPs, primarily private and public universities, and colleges offering certificate, bachelor, master and doctoral programmes.

Coincidentally in 2017, the Ministry of Education merged Polytechnic and Community College as the Department of Polytechnic and Community College (DPCCE), which oversees the HEPs in the Malaysian Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) education ecosystem. As some of these HEPs or polytechnic and community colleges known as PolyCCs are applying for MQA accreditation, the DPCCE developed an internal audit guideline for Academic Assessment (Penaziran Akademik PeNA) and Collegial and Ownership Monitoring (Pemantauan Kesepunyaan & Keserakanan PK&K) for an academic programme offered at the certificate level (Chik et al., 2019; Harun et al., 2023). Also, polytechnics and community colleges (PolyCCs) must now meet specific quality standards MQA sets for accreditation for certificate programmes. This recognition by MQA enhances the reputation and credibility of the PolyCCs, making them more attractive to prospective students and employers. It assures stakeholders that the PolyCCs as HEPs provide quality education. Therefore, this article examines the updated APA requirements stipulated in the COPPA 2017 standards and their implications on PolyCCs offering TVET programmes and vying for MQA accreditation under the DPCCE.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Academic Performance Audit (APA)

The Code of Practice for Institutional Audit identifies various institutional audits, including comprehensive, thematic, faculty-specific, and cross-faculty audits. The periodic Academic Performance Audit (APA), which assesses whether a program's accreditation status will be maintained or continued, is another type of institutional audit. The efficacy, efficiency, and general quality of the academic performance of an educational institution are evaluated systematically through an APA (Chen et al., 2020). APA examines several institution-related factors, such as curriculum design, instructional strategies, student results, assessment procedures, and support services (Ahmad & Mohd Razalli, 2014). Ahmad and Mohd Razalli added three innovations—coding, tier system, and corrective action request form—to the APA process to expedite learning. Given the increasing trend of mass higher education, the

importance of the APA has grown significantly and the rising expectations for accountability and transparency in the sector (Greere, 2022; Hauptman Komotar, 2020; Kos, 2021; Mospan & Durdas, 2021; Usman & Chinyere, 2021).

2.2 Code of Practice for Programme Accreditation (COPPA)

It is becoming increasingly crucial for the higher education ecosystem to integrate a culture of quality assurance into daily operations (Yingqiang & Yongjian, 2016). The COPPA was developed by MQA in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and the Department of Skills Development to ensure the quality of higher education programmes in Malaysia (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2008, 2017, 2019). The COPPA was modified from the Code of Practice for Quality Assurance in Public Universities (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2002). The Malaysian Qualifications Framework (MQF) sets requirements for HEPs, and COPPA is used to help them improve their programmes and ensure they comply with those standards (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2017). It is a crucial tool for ensuring quality about higher education in Malaysia (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2008, 2021).

2.3 Criteria and Standards of Evaluation

COPIA and COPPA are the foundation for the APA's standards and guidelines. These assessment areas aim to ensure that higher education programmes in Malaysia abide by the MQF requirements and offer students top-notch education that satisfies stakeholders' needs. APA provides a comprehensive framework for assessing and developing educational institutions and initiatives and includes various areas of evaluation to ensure that the Malaysian education system upholds the highest standards (Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2017). Table 1 compares APA assessment areas from COPPA 2008 versus COPPA 2017.

Table 1: Comparison of COPPA 2008 and COPPA 2017

COPPA 2008		COPPA 2017	
Area	Criteria and Standards	Area	Criteria and Standards
1	Vision, mission, educational goals as well as learning outcomes	1	Programme development and delivery
2	Curriculum delivery and design	2	Student learning assessment
3	Students' Assessment	3	Student selection and support services
4	Student selection and support	4	Academic staff
5	Academic staff	5	Educational resources
6	Educational resources	6	Programme management
7	Programme review and monitoring	7	Programme monitoring, review, and continual quality improvement
8	Leadership, governance as well as administration		
9	Continual quality improvement		

Sources: (Ahmad & Mohd Razalli, 2014; Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2008, 2017)

3. Methodology

This study employed action research comprising four steps, as shown in Figure 1. First, in Planning Stage, we conducted a document review of the COPPA 2008 and COPPA 2017 by critically reviewing the two standard documents based on the input from HEPs, assessors, specialists in quality assurance, regulators, and revisions to the accreditation requirements. The criteria and standards were matched accordingly in the two COPPA documents and will be discussed in section 4.1.

In the second stage, Acting, we collected data from APA audits conducted on four HEPs by questioning the head of programmes, deans, lecturers, and students based on APA standards.

Then at the third stage, Observing, we matched the findings of the APA audits to the new COPPA 2017 standards by analyzing the responses to the 98 standards. Lastly, during Reflecting, we evaluated the responses in terms of the objective of this study which was to explore the updated requirements of the APA and its implications for polytechnics and community colleges (PolyCCs) vying for MQA accreditation. This will be elaborated on in section 4.2.

Fig. 1: Experiential learning cycle (Kolb, 1984)

The four HEPs were randomly selected, comprising two private colleges and two private universities offering a similar certificate programme in higher education to ensure comparability with the Polytechnics and Community Colleges in TVET education pursuing accreditation under MQA. Currently, all HEPs are using COPPA 2017. The identity of the four HEPs was kept confidential due to the non-disclosure agreement signed by the auditors. These HEPs were based in different locations in Malaysia, and the APA audits were conducted on the same academic programme at the certificate level.

4. Findings and Discussions

4.1 Observations of the Code of Practice 2008 versus 2017

As shown in Figure 2 with the details provided, COPPA 2017 now has seven areas with 98 standards compared to nine areas and 181 standards of COPPA 2008. The following observations were noted based on COPPA 2017 to explain the disparities between the criteria and standards when compared to COPPA 2008:

- i. Area 1: Programme Development and Delivery - the previous standard evaluated 14 criteria compared to 17 criteria which incorporated some of the requirements in Area 2 Curriculum Design and Delivery from COPPA 2008, which previously had 25 standards. Thus, Area 1 and Area 2 for the previous guidelines are covered in Area 1, COPPA 2017.
- ii. Area 2: Assessment of Student Learning - only 11 standards are evaluated compared to 18 standards in the earlier COPPA.
- iii. Area 3: Student Selection and Support Services – the standards have only been reduced from 40 to 20.
- iv. Area 4: Academic Staff - only one difference exists between the previous (16) and updated (15) standards.

- v. Area 5: Educational Resources - only 10 standards compared to 24 standards previously.
- vi. Area 6: Programme Management - COPPA 2017 consolidated Areas 8 Leadership, Governance, and Administration from 28 to 16 standards.
- vii. Area 7: Programme Monitoring, Review, and Continual Quality Improvement - MQA combined Area 7 Programme Monitoring and Review (9) and Area 9 Continual Quality Improvements (7) into only 9 standards.

It is hoped that COPPA 2017 will simplify the APA process and assessment requirements for HEPs in higher education and TVET education to facilitate their preparation in meeting the specified quality criteria and standards.

Fig. 2. Summary of COPPA criteria and standard

Details of the COPPA 2008 and 2017 criteria and standards

COPPA 2008			COPPA 2017		
Area	Criteria	No. of standard	Area	Criteria	No. of standard
1	Vision, Mission, Educational Goals & Learning Outcomes	14	1	Programme Development and Delivery	17
1.1	Statement of Mission, Vision, and Educational Goals	6	1.1	Educational Statement Objectives of Academic Programme and Learning Outcomes	5
1.2	Participation in the formulation of Mission, Vision, and Educational Goals	2	1.2	Programme Development: Process, Content, Structure, and Learning-Teaching Methods	6
1.3	Academic Autonomy	3	1.3	Programme Delivery	6
1.4	Learning Outcomes	3			
2	Curriculum Design and Delivery	25			

COPPA 2008			COPPA 2017		
Area	Criteria	No. of standard	Area	Criteria	No. of standard
2.1	Curriculum Design and Teaching-Learning Methods	10			
2.2	Curriculum Content and Structure	3			
2.3	Management of Programmes	9			
2.4	Linkages with External Stakeholders	3			
3	Assessment of Students	18	2	Assessment of Student Learning	11
3.1	Relationship between Assessment and Learning	4	2.1	Relationship between Assessment and Learning Outcomes	2
3.2	Assessment Methods	8	2.2	Assessment Methods	4
3.3	Management of Student Assessment	6	2.3	Management of Student Assessment	5
4	Student Selection & Support Services	40	3	Student Selection and Support Services	20
4.1	Admission and Selection	14	3.1	Student Selection	5
4.2	Articulation Regulations, Credit Transfer and Credit Exemption	2	3.2	Articulation and Transfer	2
4.3	Transfer Students	3	3.3	Student Support Services	8
4.4	Student Support Services and Co-Curricular Activities	10	3.4	Student Representation and Participation	4
4.5	Student Representation and Participation	8	3.5	Alumni	1
4.6	Alumni	3			
5	Academic Staff	16	4	Academic Staff	15
5.1	Recruitment and Management	9	4.1	Recruitment and Management	8
5.2	Service and Development	7	4.2	Service and Development	7
6	Educational Resources	24	5	Educational Resources	10
6.1	Physical Facilities	9	5.1	Physical Facilities	4
6.2	Research and Development	6	5.2	Research and Development	3
6.3	Educational Expertise	2	5.3	Financial Resources	3
6.4	Educational Exchanges	3			
6.5	Financial Allocation	4			
8	Leadership, Governance, and Administration	28	6	Programme Management	16
8.1	Governance	12	6.1	Programme Management	6
8.2	Institutional and Academic Leadership	6	6.2	Programme Leadership	3
8.3	Administrative and Management Staff	4	6.3	Administrative Staff	3
8.4	Academic Records	3	6.4	Academic Records	4
8.5	Interaction with External Sectors	2			
7	Programme Monitoring and Review	9	7	Programme Monitoring, Review, and Continual Quality Improvement	9
7.1	Mechanism for Programme Monitoring and Review	6	7.1	Mechanisms for Programme Monitoring, Review, and Continual Quality Improvement	9
7.2	Involvement of Stakeholders	3			

COPPA 2008			COPPA 2017		
Area	Criteria	No. of standard	Area	Criteria	No. of standard
9	Continual Quality Improvement	7			9
9.1	Quality Improvement	7			9.1
	Total	181		Total	98

Source: (Ahmad & Mohd Razalli, 2014; Malaysian Qualification Agency, 2008, 2017)

4.2 Implications of updated COPPA 2017 to Polytechnic and Community Colleges

Table 2 shows the results of the second step of this study. The aggregate responses of the APA audit exercises of the four HEPs are presented as to whether they have met or did not meet the standards stipulated in the COPPA 2017. Due to confidentiality, we cannot disclose how many standards were met or not met by each HEP in this paper, only the combined general comments for illustration as supported by the literature.

Based on Table 2, out of the seven areas, Area 1 Programme Development and Delivery and Area 2 Assessment of Student Learning seemed to be the most problematic areas for the four auditees HEPs to meet the stipulated standards (Kausar, 2022; Liu & Clayton, 2016; Mbua et al., 2022; Oviawe et al., 2021). In Area 1, the auditors highlighted concerns about the alignment of PEOs and PLOs with Basic Course Standards and MQF (2nd Edition). CLOs need improvement, with some courses being incompatible and lacking sub-topics. Based on the COPPA 2017, the auditors recommended HEPs should provide at least three CLOs for each course and update outdated reference materials. The Book of Knowledge (BoK) needs revision, and a clear programme pathway should be provided for students. In Area 2, the auditors noted that the courses focused on GCF 2019. It is recommended that assignments should replace exams for better evaluation and HEPs needs to revise the grading scale for distinctions in grades.

In addition, the auditors also noted that counsellor information was incomplete Area 3. HEPs must provide certificates and other documents needed to verify qualifications and meet licensing requirements (Burns, 2020; Miao, 2022). Academic staff in Area 4 are a concern due to possible lack of qualifications and inconsistent information provided. The Employee Handbook needs to clarify annual training allocation for staff development and education quality (Gerhardt & Karsan, 2022; Musakuro, 2022). The auditors noted that Area 5 has outdated reference materials for the programme as well as missing some important ones. This could hinder students' learning experience (Abumandour, 2021). In Area 6, the Head of the Programme lacks the necessary academic qualifications for the certificate programme being applied. A competent leader with relevant expertise is crucial for effective administration. In Area 7, the auditors recommend that HEPs should implement the Foundation Course Programme based on the GCF 2019 for standardized and structured university studies (Schultz-Jones et al., 2021; Tuzlukova et al., 2019).

Table 2. Examples of Findings from the Audit of 4 HEPs based on COPPA 2017

Area	COPPA 2017 Criteria	Meet Standard (based on the 4 HEPs audited)	Do not Meet the Standard (based on the 4 HEPs audited)
1	Programme Development and Delivery		
1.1	Statement of Educational Objectives of Academic	Autonomy - HEP has autonomy in program development and delivery.	Programme Educational Objectives (PEO) - Should be clear and suitable for offering this program; refer to the

<p>Programme and Learning Outcomes</p>	<p>Guidelines of Curriculum: Foundation (GCF) MQA (2019)</p>	<p>Basic Course Standard 2014, GCF 2019, or MQF 2nd Edition to refine this PEO.</p>
	<p>Program curriculum is adapted fully</p>	<p>Programme Learning Outcomes (PLO)s</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All PLOs are unsuitable. Since HEP has arranged the program curriculum structure based on GCF 2019, HEP needs to refine the existing PLO as recommended by the Basic Course Standards 2014, GCF 2019, and MQF 2nd Edition. <p>Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CLO does not measure the level it should - Courses offered are not compatible with the programme - Courses with CLO statements and mapping are not accurate. HEP was asked to make improvements to the CLO-PLO mapping. - Courses that do not provide sub-topics. HEP needs to include sub-topics on each content. - CLO should be at C3 level for quantitative courses because students need to know how to apply what they have learned. - HEP must coordinate the same course code in all the information provided. - HEP to make at least 3 CLOs for each course to ensure that the learning outcomes are balanced and achievable.
<p>1.2 Programme Development: Process, Content, Structure, and Learning-Teaching Methods</p>	<p>Curriculum Development Design Team (CDDT) and Studies Committee</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the committee has scheduled the curriculum course offering. 	<p>Programme Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confusing and disorganized. Does not comply with the Guideline of Curriculum (Foundation) 2019. <p>Reference materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Courses have main and additional reference materials not up-to-date. HEP was asked to update the reference material five years ago (2018 and above).
<p>1.3 Programme Delivery</p>		<p>Some courses do not provide additional reference materials</p> <p>Body of Knowledge (BOK)</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Courses need to be dropped as they were not in the BOK <p>Pathway</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HEP does not state clearly the pathway for this programme.
2	Assessment of Student Learning		
2.1	Relationship between Assessment and Learning Outcomes		Most of the courses offered are taken from the GCF 2019 but some courses have changed evaluation methods and are not guided by the GCF
2.2	Assessment Methods	<p>Assessment Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The overall evaluation method and material management system follow GCF MQA (2019). - The continuous assessment method (course work) for all courses HEP will use is by GCF MQA (2019). 	<p>Assessment Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need to be improved and not be exam- oriented. - HEP is advised to change the mid- semester exam to an assignment emphasizing skills as stated in the course content (Transferable skills). - The grading scale does not show honors, pass or fail grades. - HEP was asked to realign the full grading scale.
2.3	Management of Student Assessment	<p>Assessment management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Procedures are prepared and monitored by the Exam Board. 	
3	Student Selection and Support Services		
3.1	Student Selection	Overall, entry eligibility requirements and student selection methods are appropriate and in line with GCF MQA (2019) and Basic Program Standards (2014).	
3.2	Articulation and Transfer		
3.3	Student Support Services		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No information about the counselor is attached. - The HEP counselor's biennial practice certificate license must be attached, and relevant supporting documents related to this counselor - appointment and acceptance letter.
3.4	Student Representation and Participation		
3.5	Alumni		
4	Academic Staff		
4.1	Recruitment and Management	<p>Overall, Area 4 is satisfactory.</p> <p>HEP lists ten permanent academic staff and one part-time qualified Bachelor's Degree and above - suitable.</p> <p>HEP also has an appropriate academic staff teaching load policy (maximum 18-20 hours per week).</p>	<p>There are academic staff who are not suitable to teach the courses offered.</p> <p>No course information is taught by academic staff.</p> <p>Information about academic staff is inconsistent.</p> <p>There is a mismatch between the academic qualifications of the academic staff teaching the introductory course</p>

4.2	Service and Development	HEP provides professional development courses and programs and involves academic staff in formulating and revising the curriculum	Training Hours - No information regarding the allocation of annual training hours for academic staff in the Employee Handbook. (Programme Standard states that the HEP needs to allocate 40 hours a year of training - Continuous Professional Development).
5	Educational Resources	Overall, the information in Area 5 is satisfactory.	All the list of reference materials in the appendix (OC Library Books) is not up-to-date.
5.1	Physical Facilities	HEP has two qualified librarians	Main and additional reference materials are missing and not up-to-date.
5.2	Research and Development		
5.3	Financial Resources		
6	Programme Management		
6.1	Programme Management	Head of Programme - appropriate and qualified	Head of the Programme - not suitable for the program applied for because he does not have the relevant academic qualifications at the bachelor's degree level. - has academic qualifications outside the scope of the program field. Inappropriate.
6.2	Programme Leadership		
6.3	Administrative Staff		
6.4	Academic Records		
7	Programme Monitoring, Review, and Continual Quality Improvement		
7.1	Mechanisms for Programme Monitoring, Review, and Continual Quality Improvement	Overall, Area 7 is satisfactory	The Malaysian Qualifications Framework (MQF) does not include the Foundation Course Program. Still, the MQF defines this programme and states the generic characteristics of this level so that the abilities of students entering university are aligned and comparable (Foundation Course Standard 2014, page letter 1; MQF 2nd Edition, page 23). - HEP is requested to run this program based on the Guidelines of Curriculum: Foundation 2019 in total.
Total			

The revised COPPA 2017 accreditation has several implications for the quality assurance process under DPCCE, the HEPs or PolyCCs involved, the internal auditors, and the APA process. Firstly, as discussed earlier, the DPCCE developed an internal audit guideline for Academic Assessment (PeNA) and Collegial and Ownership Monitoring (PK&K) for the academic programme offered (Chik et al., 2019; Harun et al., 2023). PeNA and PK&K audit instruments consisted of criteria for MQA accreditation and compliance to MS ISO 9001:2015 standard certification for PolyCCs as required in the TVET education ecosystem. The Governance and Excellence Section organises the internal audit under DPCCE. Each PolyCC

will undergo annual monitoring and audit assessments by DPCCE-certified auditors to determine the level of academic quality the institution offers. Therefore, the first implication is for the DPCCE to ratify the APA process required by MQA vis-à-vis PeNA and PK&K processes, as they may be duplicative and not mutually exclusive.

Second, as stated in COPPA 2017, the monitoring and assessment criteria are not exhaustive. The new code also strongly emphasised quality assurance and ongoing improvement to raise educational standards and outcomes in technical and vocational institutions. To comply with the requirements for MQA Full Accreditation (FA) or Compliance Audit (CA), PolyCCs must complete a self-review audit (SRR) within three years of receiving Provisional Accreditation (PA). However, few PolyCC, primarily those subject to MQA audits, did not conduct SRR. The implication for the HEPs or PolyCCs under DPCCE is that they must conduct self-review audits or SRR per MQA requirements, including those not vying for MQA accreditation and evaluation, in addition to the ISO certification under TVET education.

Third, the DPCCE internal auditors and the APA process experienced significant changes due to the updated Code of Practice from 2008 to 2017. The APA process involves auditors impacted by the amended Code of Practice (Irawan & McIntyre-Mills, 2016; Lawal et al., 2022). The revised Code of Practice under DPCCE resulted in several technical and vocational education improvements. The updated code increased the importance of industrial relevance and alignment, ensuring that educational programmes were created to satisfy the needs and requirements of the labour market (Pujiawati et al., 2022). This change resulted in a more skill-based and practical curriculum, better preparing graduates with the skills they need for employment (Li et al., 2023; Mia et al., 2022). To successfully examine and evaluate institutions' compliance with the new code's requirements, auditors must become familiar with them. They had to modify their auditing procedures and methods to comply with the upgraded requirements. Auditors' roles became vital to ensure that an institution meets the enhanced quality requirements and criteria specified in the amended code (Axelsen et al., 2017; Rahayu et al., 2020). Thus, the implication for the DPCCE internal auditors is how and where to assign the results of the APA audit conducted in the respective MQA, PeNA, and PK&K instruments, as the MQA accreditation and ISO 9001:2015 certification serve different purposes and utilities for the TVET and higher education ecosystem.

Lastly, the revised COPPA 2017 significantly affected the APA process. It provided new requirements for institutions to follow while conducting audits, including criteria, standards, and guidance. A more thorough inspection of an institution's academic performance, curriculum, teaching methods, assessment practices, student support services, and adherence to the code is all part of the audit process, which has grown increasingly rigorous. The revised COPPA 2017 also emphasized the value of self-evaluation and ongoing development, calling for institutions to regularly conduct internal audits and reviews to track and improve academic performance (Politis, 2018; Sugiarno, 2018). Overall, COPPA 2017 significantly impacted positive developments by guaranteeing industrial relevance, raising educational standards, and promoting quality assurance in technical and vocational institutions. Therefore, the implication for the APA process is how to maintain its relevance among PolyCCs and for the DPCCE to uphold quality assurance of their academic programmes and TVET education.

5. Conclusion

The amended COPPA 2017 significantly impacted the development of Malaysia's TVET education ecosystem comprising the polytechnic and community colleges or PolyCCs under DPCCE. Positive adjustments brought about by the code revisions immediately impacted the TVET industry besides the stated implications for DPCCE, the PolyCCs, internal auditors and the APA process. First, the revised code strongly emphasized the importance of industrial

relevance, ensuring that TVET programmes are created to satisfy the changing requirements of the labour market. This focus ultimately helped graduates become more job-ready and improved their employability by bridging the gap between the skills they had learned through TVET education offered by the PolyCCs and what companies were looking for.

Second, by supporting competency-based education and bringing TVET programmes offered by the PolyCCs in line with industry best practices, the new code upped the bar for their level of excellence. The code fostered high-quality education and training within the TVET sector by establishing higher-quality benchmarks, leading to better student results and overall programme effectiveness in the PolyCCs. The new MQA regulations also emphasized industry participation, encouraging stronger collaborations between PolyCCs as TVET institutions and businesses to advance the growth of the TVET education ecosystem. This cooperative strategy acknowledged the value of including corporations, professional organizations, and industry experts in developing and delivering TVET programmes. These partnerships ensured that TVET education aligned with contemporary company practices gave students the needed skills, and offered work-based learning opportunities and internships. These business partnerships helped Malaysia's ecosystem for TVET education to grow overall.

Finally, the revised guideline acknowledged the importance of earlier learning and urged PolyCCs as TVET institutions to evaluate and recognize people's prior experiences and skills. The ability to receive credit for prior knowledge and skills allowed learners to move through the learning process more quickly, enter programmes at a higher level, or move up the corporate ladder. Acknowledging prior learning improved the inclusion and accessibility of TVET education in Malaysia. Therefore, the revised COPPA 2017 enhanced quality assurance in the Malaysian TVET education ecosystem. It emphasized applicability to industry, raised quality requirements, encouraged industry cooperation, and acknowledged the importance of past learning. Together, these initiatives helped the TVET sector develop and thrive, improving the sector's responsiveness to industry demands, the standard of education and training, and the employability of TVET graduates as talent outputs of the Malaysian polytechnic and community colleges.

Glossary

APA	Academic Performance Audit
COPIA	Code of Practice for Institutional Audit
COPPA	Code of Practice for Programme Accreditation
DPCCE	Department of Polytechnic and Community College Education
GCF	Guidelines of Curriculum: Foundation
HEPs	Higher Education Providers
MQA	Malaysian Qualification Agency
MQF	Malaysian Qualification Framework
MyHE 4.0	Malaysian Higher Education 4.0
PeNA	<i>Penaziran Akademik</i> (Academic Assessment)
PK&K	<i>Pemantauan Kesympunaan & Keserakanan</i> (Collegial and Ownership Monitoring)
PolyCC	Polytechnics and Community Colleges
TVET	Technical and Vocational Education and Training

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